

IDERHA is an open platform designed to enable connectivity, access, sharing, use and reuse of digital health data. Our policy recommendations will enhance regulatory and HTA decision making, facilitating access to digital health innovations for patients and health care professionals.

Transforming data into better healthcare

In recent years, there has been an exponential growth in the generation of data that could be harnessed for use in healthcare delivery and research. Health data is highly heterogeneous in nature, which means it comes from many different sources and technologies, for example, MRI images, genetic profiles, an individual patient's health record, and much more. However, accessing and combining these data sources to gain new insights or draw meaningful conclusions for patients and research, is extremely challenging.

IDERHA (Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance)

The IDERHA project aims to create a scalable digital platform which can combine different data sources. This will equip healthcare professionals, patients, and researchers with

new capabilities to improve patient outcomes. The platform that IDERHA will be creating will use common standards and practices, leading to more personalized health care for patients via tools that are built on these different data sources. To enable patients and health care providers to benefit from novel health solutions, IDERHA also seeks to accelerate policy development. Informed by patient needs, we will develop consensus recommendations for fully compliant health data access and sharing. This may lead to a framework for data governance that can be used as a model globally.

Lung cancer as EU's key priority

IDERHA will focus on lung cancer, which is one of the key priorities of the Europe Beating Cancer program. The project will link and analyse diverse data of a lung cancer patient's journey: from early screening of citizens at risk, to development of lung cancer, to remote monitoring of late-stage patients to enable better care in an at-home

setting. Ultimately, the platform and policy recommendations will be disease independent.

Accelerate policy development

To enable patients and health care providers to benefit from novel health solutions, IDERHA also seeks to accelerate policy development. Informed by patient needs, we will develop consensus recommendations for fully compliant health data access and sharing, as well as for the acceptability of heterogeneous health research results for regulatory and HTA decision-making. This may lead to a framework for data governance that can be used as a model globally.

Patient Advisory Board

The patient perspective is a crucial factor in the IDERHA project, which will be implemented by the Patient Advisory Board (PAB). The PAB will consist of people who have experienced lung cancer and patient representatives; their main goal in the project is to monitor and review IDERHA activities from the patient perspective. In addition, the PAB will play an advisory role in several key aspects of the project and will help to disseminate and communicate about the project to their communities.

Public consultation

IDERHA recognises the importance of involving key stakeholders as well as the general public in its work. Therefore, a public consultation phase is critical for gathering insights, opinions, and concerns from patients, healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the general public. To achieve this, IDERHA actively engages with the general public through open webinars, feedback forms on the website, and an annual Public Forum that coincides with the Annual Consortium Meeting. In 2024, the Public Forum will be held in Berlin on 15 April. Please reach out to communications@iderha.org or visit our web page for more information.

'IDERHA is a pioneering project focussed on creating health care solutions that integrate diverse health data, to bring improved care and treatments for patients.'

KEY FACTS

IDERHA leadership & management:

IDERHA is led by the Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology ITMP and Johnson & Johnson Medical GmbH, part of Johnson & Johnson MedTech.

The management team consists of Dr. Philip Gribbon (Fraunhofer ITMP) and Dr. Christian Muehlendyck MD (Johnson & Johnson MEDICAL GmbH).

Consortium partners:

33 academic, clinical, medtech, pharmaceutical, IT and patient advocacy organizations as well as public authorities from across the EU and the world.

Funding:

IDERHA is among the first projects funded through the EU Innovative Health Initiative (IHI), a public-private partnership (PPP) between the EU and the European life science industries. IDERHA's total budget is € 42.7 mln (plus contributions from Associated Partners from Switzerland and the UK).

Duration:

IDERHA will run for 5 years, from 1 April 2023 - 31 March 2028.

More information:

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